

Large Area CVD Monolayer Graphene for Nanoelectronics: Device Performance and Analysis

Osama M. Nayfeh and Madan Dubey

United States Army Research Laboratory, Sensors and Electron Devices Directorate

2800 Powder Mill Road, Adelphi, MD 20783

osama.nayfeh@us.army.mil; madan.dubey@us.army.mil

Abstract—Graphene transistors using large area CVD monolayer graphene are constructed and examined. Back-gated devices with exposed graphene channels are characterized to shed light on some of the apparent doping and transport effects that could impact the device performance. Electrical measurements under vacuum and soft-anneal conditions are used to modulate the effective doping density and carrier mobility for both electrons and holes. A good agreement between measurements and a simple drift-diffusion model is obtained when modeling this CVD graphene with a net p-type doping and asymmetric electron/hole mobility. An extracted mean-free path for scattering suggests the presence of large levels of Coulomb and short-range scattering which could be limiting the mobility in this doped material. The results are of importance for understanding the potential of large-area CVD graphene for use in future radiofrequency devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

Graphene is a potentially useful material for future transistors because of its excellent transport properties and its nature as a 2D sheet with atomic thickness provides a possible route for extremely scaled devices with electrostatic integrity [1-4]. In addition, new circuit concepts that have been developed for the general class of ambipolar devices [5] have potential for implementation with the graphene system such as radiofrequency multipliers, mixers, and also logic inverters [6-8]. Recently, there have been rapid advances on the growth of large-area monolayer and few-layer graphene via metal-catalyzed (typically Ni or Cu) atmospheric and low-pressure chemical vapor deposition processes and the subsequent transfer of the graphene to SiO₂ [9-10]. There are reports that this synthesis method has been scaled up by a roll-to-roll process in a manufacturing setting to produce 30" sheets of material [11], opening the possibility of new advanced devices in this material system. In addition, due to the ability to transfer CVD graphene to a range of substrates and to deposit advanced dielectrics, the design space of CVD based graphene FETs could be potentially tailored for

enhanced functionality. However, due to the nature of growth and transfer, chemical modification of the graphene could occur due to the conditions and metallic catalyst. The typical reported carrier mobility of CVD graphene is significantly lower than exfoliated or on-SiC material due potentially to different impurity/doping levels and material quality. Elucidating the carrier scattering sources in metal catalyzed CVD graphene and understanding the device operation is essential for realizing high mobility material for both holes and electrons and for improving the performance of GFETs. In this work, back-gated devices with exposed graphene channel are constructed in order to understand aspects of the doping and transport effects that could be limiting aspects of the device performance. A drift-diffusion model is used to model the device characteristics to produce a good agreement with measurements for a p-type doped film with asymmetric electron/hole mobility. Examination of an extracted mean-free path for scattering shows that the mobility in the case of these devices is likely limited by large levels of Coulomb and short-range scattering. The results are of importance for determining the potential of large-area CVD graphene for use in future electronics devices.

II. BACK-GATED GRAPHENE TRANSISTORS

In order to shed light on some aspects of the doping and carrier transport effects and possible performing limiting factors, back-gated FET test-structures with exposed graphene channel were constructed and examined. Graphene-on-SiO₂ was synthesized via Cu catalyzed CVD and subsequently transferred to 300nm SiO₂/n+ Si substrates. Cr/Au (5nm/90nm) source/drain contact pads were deposited using e-beam evaporation and formed by lift-off (Figure 1). Large area Raman mapping (Figure 2) shows predominately single monolayer material with some disruptions due to wrinkles. The FET I-V characteristics were measured under vacuum (5 mTorr) and in-situ annealing (375 K) in a desert cryogenics probe station.

Fig 1: Cross section (left) and top-view (right) schematic of the back-gated graphene transistors. The thickness of the SiO₂ gate-insulator is 300 nm and the source/drain Cr/Au is 5nm/90nm.

Fig 2: Raman mapping across a $12\mu\text{m} \times 12\mu\text{m}$ perimeter region. The large area CVD material is predominately monolayer graphene.

Figure 3 shows the typical electrical measurement results taken with increasing exposure time of the device to vacuum conditions. Increasing vacuum duration results in a shift in the Dirac point towards neutral voltage levels, with a shift of ~ 40 V after 3 days. This direction and magnitude of voltage shifting suggests the removal of significant quantities of “p-type” doping via exposure to the vacuum. It is highly likely that adsorbed O and OH (behaving p-type) are adsorbed on the graphene during processing and/or exposure to ambient. Soft annealing of the devices under vacuum (Figure 4) at slightly elevated temperatures (375 K) further shifts the Dirac point so that both electron and hole branches of the current are observed within a 120 V range. As evidenced by device hysteresis measurements (Figure 5), the density of insulator trapped charge is significantly smaller than the density of effective charged “dopant”.

Fig 3: Measurements in ambient and vacuum. Removal of adsorbed species reduces the effective p-type doping level and modulates the mobility.

Fig 4: Measurements after annealing under vacuum. Annealing further reduces the doping and modulates the mobility of electrons and holes.

Fig 5: Hysteresis measurements; the extracted density of trapped charges in the thermal SiO_2 insulator is significantly less than the density of “dopant” charges.

III. DEVICE MODELING AND ANALYSIS

A drift-diffusion model coupled to a solution of the Poisson equation is solved in a conventional device simulator and is used to model the measured characteristics. Figure 6 shows a good agreement between simulations and measurements when modeling the graphene as a “semiconductor” with zero energy gap, heavy p-type (volumetric) doping of $1.3 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, peak hole mobility of $530 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ and peak electron mobility of $280 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, implying a scattering dominated transport regime. There is a slight deviation near the trough in the characteristics and is attributed to non-idealities present in the system.

In the simulations, the expression for the density of states with energy is modified to approximate a graphene-like linear density of states and the overall integrated carrier concentration (of holes and electrons) versus gate-voltage is approximated well to first order (producing a descent match to the $I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}}$ ratio) and is mainly determined by the size of the energy gap and the carrier mobility used.

In addition to a neutral-directed shift in the Dirac point, there is a measured change in the slope of the I-V characteristics, suggesting co-modulation of both the hole and electron mobility. As shown in Figure 7, examination of this mobility dependence as a function of the removed charged “doping” density reveals that the apparent increase in mobility is larger for the holes than the electrons in the p-type material. The extracted low-field carrier mean-free-path for back-scattering in this doped p-type CVD graphene material is extracted for both holes and electrons from the measured experimental data. From the dispersion relationship for “monolayer” graphene

$$E(k) = \pm \hbar v_F k$$

and the expected Fermi velocity

$$v(k) = v_F \approx 10^8 \text{ cm/s}$$

an expression for the density of states $D(E)$ and carrier density, n_s vs. Fermi energy, E_f are calculated as

$$D(E) = \frac{2|E|}{\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2}$$

and

$$n_s(E_F) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{E_F}{\hbar v_F} \right)^2.$$

Based on the measured gate-insulator capacitance C_{ins} and the measured voltage level of the Dirac point (V_{DP}), the charge density can be estimated as

$$qn_s = C_{ins}(V_g - V_{DP}).$$

Using the Landauer expression [12], the conductivity, G_s , can be calculated (for long gate-lengths) as

$$G_s(E_F) = \frac{2q^2}{\hbar} \lambda(E_F) \frac{2E_F}{\pi \hbar v_F}$$

and an expression for the low-field mean-free-path for back-scattering, $\lambda(E_f)$ as a function of the Fermi energy

$$\lambda(E_F) = \frac{G_s(V_g)/(2q^2/\hbar)}{2\sqrt{n_s(V_g)}/\pi}.$$

Figure 8 shows the extracted $\lambda(E_f)$ from low-field measurements of back-gated GFETs taken under ambient and vacuum conditions for a range of E_f . The dependence of the mean-free-path with increasing carrier energy is a specific signature of the presence of large levels of Coulomb scattering. It is likely that scattering from charged impurities adsorbed on the graphene, incorporated in the graphene during growth and from the interaction with the substrate contribute to the overall degree of scattering. Also, the weak dependence of the minimum conductivity point of the I-V characteristics with reduced levels of “doping” support a scattering limiting regime of transport consistent with other samples reported in the literature with large levels of impurities [13-14]. For the electrons, the energy dependence of the mean-free-path at higher carrier energies also suggests the contribution of short range scattering likely due to the disorder in the form of defects in the graphene lattice or

roughness that could contribute to the overall response (which clearly are apparent in the material meteorology). The asymmetry in the dependence between the electrons and holes could be due to screening effects which alter the behavior of some of the scattering mechanisms based on charge carrier type, and also the presence of interactions with carrier energy-dependent surface states. Figure 12 also shows the measured temperature dependence of the I-V characteristics within the 77-300 K. The weakness of the temperature dependence on the minimum conductivity point supports a scattering limiting regime of transport that is dominated by both Coulomb and short-range scattering [15-17] in these samples. The slight temperature dependence of the characteristics above 250 K may be due to the role of ripples and wrinkles, whose presence is clearly apparent in the AFM measurements.

Fig 6: Measurements vs. simulations (in the scattering limited regime). The “doping” concentration, charge density, and mobility of electrons and holes are extracted from inverse modeling.

Fig 7: Extracted mobility for majority (holes) and minority (electrons) carriers as a function of the density of “dopant” charges removed with exposure to vacuum and annealing.

The results therefore suggest the improvement of the mobility by reducing the various scattering mechanisms, and increasing the carrier mean-free-path should be possible. By growing higher quality material, obtaining better control of doping, limiting defects and reducing substrate interactions, it is expected that the mobility and frequency performance of graphene FETs based on CVD graphene will continue to improve.

Fig 8: Extraction of carrier mean-free-path for back-scattering $\lambda(E_F)$ as a function of the Fermi energy (E_F). The hole mobility is limited by Coulomb scattering whereas the electron mobility is limited by a combination of Coulomb scattering and short range scattering for this p-type doped CVD graphene.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We constructed field effect transistors using chemical-vapor-deposited monolayer graphene and used electrical measurements under ambient and vacuum conditions to analyze some important physical aspects of the minority carrier mobility behavior. We measured a dependency between shifting of the Dirac Point directed towards neutral levels under soft vacuum/annealing conditions and an increase in the extracted low-field carrier mobility. Reduction in the effective p-type “doping” of the graphene results in an increase of the carrier mobility of both the electrons and majority, with a stronger majority carrier dependency. The measured I-V characteristics of the devices are modeled (in the scattering limited regime) using a simple drift/diffusion model implemented in a continuum simulator. Using this model, the effective doping density, carrier concentration, and mobility are extracted for electrons and holes. Analysis of the energy dependency of the carrier mean-free-path for back-scattering, suggests that the mobility in this

CVD material is limited by large levels of Coulomb and short-range scattering.

REFERENCES

1. K. S. Novoselov, A. K. Geim, S. V. Morozov, D. Jiang, Y. Zhang, S. V. Dubonos, I. V. Grigorieva, and A. A. Firsov, “Electric field effect in atomically thin carbon films,” *Science*, vol. 306, no. 5696, pp. 666–669, Oct. 2004.
2. F. Schwierz, “Graphene Transistors,” *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 5, pp. 487–496, July, 2010.
3. K. Geim and K. S. Novoselov, “The rise of graphene,” *Nature Materials*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 183–191, Mar. 2007.
4. S. V. Morozov, K. S. Novoselov, M. I. Katsnelson, F. Schedin, D. C. Elias, J. A. Jaszczak, and A. K. Geim, “Giant intrinsic carrier mobilities in graphene,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 100, 016602, 2008.
5. F. Pregelidiny, J-B. Kammerer, and C. Lallement, “Compact Modeling and Applications of CNTFETs for Analog and Digital Circuit Design,” in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Electronic, Circuits, and Systems*, pp. 130-133, 2006.
6. H. Wang, D. Nezich, J. Kong, T. Palacios, “Graphene Frequency Multipliers,” *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 30, no. 5, 2009.
7. N. Harada, K. Yagi, S. Sato, and N. Yokoyama, “A polarity-controllable graphene inverter,” *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 96, 012102, 2010.
8. R. Sordan, F. Traversi, and V. Russo, “Logic gates with a single graphene transistor,” *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 94, 073305, 2009.
9. A. Piner, I. Velamakanni, E. Jung, E. Tutuc, S. K. Banerjee, L. Colombo, and R. S. Ruoff, “Large-area synthesis of high-quality and uniform graphene films on copper foils,” *Science Express Reports*, vol. 324, no. 5932, 2009.
10. A. Reina, X. Jia, J. Ho, D. Nezich, H. Son, V. Bulovic, M. S. Dresselhaus, and J. Kong, “Large area, few-layer graphene films on arbitrary substrates by chemical vapor deposition,” *Nano Letters*, vol. 9, no. 30, 2009.
11. S. Bae, H.K. Kim, Y.B. Lee, X.F. Xu, J.S. Park, Y. Zheng, J. Balakrishnan, T. Lei, H.R. Kim, Y. Song, Y-J. Kim, K. S. Kim, B. Ozyilmaz, A-H. Ahn, B.H. Hong, and S. Ijima, “Roll-to-Roll Production of 30-Inch Graphene Films for Transparent Electrodes,” *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 5, pp. 574–578, June, 2010.
12. R Landauer, “Conductance determined by transmission: probes and quantised constriction resistance,” *Journal of Physics: Condensed. Matter*, vol. 1, pp. 8099-8110, 1989.
13. S. Adam, E.H. Hwang, V.M. Galitski, and S. Das Sarma, “A self-consistent theory for graphene transport,” *PNAS*, vol. 104, no. 47, pp. 18392-18397, November, 2007.
14. Y.-W. Tan, Y. Zhang, K. Bolotin, Y. Zhao, S. Adam, E.H. Hwang, S. Das Sarma, H.L. Stormer, and P. Kim, “Measurement of Scattering Rate and Minimum Conductivity in Graphene,” *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 99, 246803, December, 2007.
15. J.-H. Chen, C. Jang, S. Xiao, M. Ishigami, and M.S. Fuhrer, “Intrinsic and extrinsic performance limits of graphene devices on SiO₂,” *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 3, pp. 206-209, April 2008.
16. J.-H. Chen, C. Jang, S. Adam, M. S. Fuhrer, E. D. Williams, and M. Ishigami, “Charged-impurity scattering in graphene,” *Nature Physics*, vol. 4, pp. 377 – 381, April, 2008.
17. A. H. Castro Neto, F. Guinea, N. M. R. Peres, K. S. Novoselov and A. K. Geim, “The electronic properties of graphene,” *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, vol. 81, pp. 109-162, 2009.